

Supporting Holistic Student Development through Online Community Building

Dr. Savita Madhavrao Gire

Vice Principal, Assistant Professor

Dadasaheb Jotiram Godse Arts Commerce Science College Vaduj Dist. Satara -415506.

ABSTRACT -

Holistic learning is an extensive approach to teaching, where teachers seek to manage emotional, social, ethical, and academic needs of students in a coherent learning format. Importance is placed on a positive atmosphere in schools and providing academic and nonacademic support to students. Students are taught to contemplate their actions and how they impact their community- globally and locally, and how to learn from the community around them. Holistic education encompasses a wide range of philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices. Its focus is on wholeness, and it attempts to avoid excluding any significant aspects of the human experience. It is an eclectic and inclusive movement whose main characteristic is the idea that educational experiences foster a less materialistic and a more spiritual worldview along with more dynamic and holistic views of reality. It also proposes that educational experience promote a more balanced development of and cultivate the relationship among the different aspects of the individual (intellectual, physical, spiritual, emotional, social and Aesthetic), as well as the relationships between the individual and other people, the individual and natural environment, the inner- self of students and external. Holistic education is concerned with life experience, not with narrowly defined" basic skills".

Holistic education has become a familiar topic in current educational literature. There are various opinions about what holistic education represents and a single definition remains elusive. It can be defined as a philosophy and pedagogy of education based on development of wholeness

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

of individuals. Holistic education addresses the broadest development of the whole person i.e. physical, intellectual, spiritual, emotional, social and aesthetic aspects. It aims for the optimum possible human development enabling a person to become the very best or finest that they can be and develop fully 'those capacities that together make up a human being' (Forbes, 2003). It is an approach which aims to encompass all aspects of personal learning, growth and development of individual. Holistic education based on the premises that each person finds identity, meaning and purpose of life by connecting to the surrounding environment. The purpose of holistic education is not only to prepare students for academic success, but also enable them to learn the challenges of living as a whole that means learning about themselves, about healthy relationships, social responsibilities and humanitarian values. In holistic education, to educate young people means helping them bring forth their creativity, their compassion, their curiosity, their moral and aesthetic sensitivity, their critical intellectual skills, their ability to participate in a robust democracy- in a word, their wholeness. Holistic education focuses on the optimum possible development of the students, encouraging them to become the very best or finest that they can be and enable them to experience all they can form their life and reach their goals. Education with holistic perspective is concerned with the development of each student's intellectual, emotional, social, physical, aesthetic, and spiritual potentials. Holistic education is aim to nourish the inherent possibilities of human development. Holistic education prepares a student for lifelong learning and moves them towards the life skills, attitudes and personal awareness that the student will need in an increasingly complex world. Holistic education has the capacity to lead the students into new areas of thinking, broaden their personal and critical thinking and develop an appreciation of the world around them. Holistic education is not to be defined as a particular method or technique; it must be seen as a paradigm, a set of basic assumptions and principles with some features that can be applied in schools in diverse ways. Some principles of holistic education are as follows – i) Educating for human development: Education is to nourish the inherent possibilities of human development. It focuses on optimum possible development of student's i.e. physical, intellectual, emotional, social, aesthetic etc. It teaches children about themselves, about their relationships. ii) Honoring students as individual: Each learner is unique; they have individual needs and abilities. Holistic education is based on personal differences. iii) Based on child centric approach: Holistic education based on child centric approach. Student need to work at their own pace. Its emphasis on diverse learning style of the students. Holistic education is a radical endeavor. The educational journey starts the process of self-actualization through relationships and interconnectedness with other individuals, groups and the world around them is an integral part. Formal education is merely the starting point of this life long process. It prepares the students to meet the challenges of living. It is an educational journey of personal discovery starting within formal education then continues throughout of life. Teachers often engage students in assignments that apply critical-thinking skills toward solving real-world problems. As indicated by UNESCO, education for sustainable development needs a holistic

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

approach. In this perspective, pro-quality education plays a double role—it includes contents that are innovative and closely related to sustainable development and it is a link connecting other activities of the educational system to achieve the objectives of education for sustainable development. This issue, as overlooked in most countries, is an attractive educational innovation, which can affect shaping students' attitudes in a more effective way. For the purpose of this research, the author collected secondary data as a result of literature analysis, mostly including governing and archival acts of law, as well as raw data with the use of a diagnostic survey method with a questionnaire survey technique. The main stage of this method was collecting research data through surveying students, representatives of teaching staff, and school principals from schools in Poland. Research conducted by the author supported the proposed hypothesis, according to which the Polish educational system is not oriented towards shaping the pro-quality attitude of high school students.

Review of Literature:

Holistic education represents a new movement that began in the mid-1980s and is a philosophy of education based on the understanding that identity, purpose, and meaning are developed through community connections, natural world connections, and humanitarian values (Spier, Leenknecht, & Osher, 2018). Holistic education is based on a reverence and passion for life and learning, including experiential learning, and recognizes the significance of relationships and primary human values in the educational facility. Thus, the core concepts of holistic education are not new because of the emphasis on character education and virtue- and values-development (J. Miller, 2019). The explicit application of holistic ideas to education involves the work of multiple theorists, including Froebel, Rousseau, Thoreau, Alcott, Emerson, Pestalozzi, Steiner, Freire, Montessori, Parker, Illich, Dewey, Goodman, Holt, Rogers, Egan, Maslow, Gardner, Jung, and Krishnamurti (J. Miller, 2019). It is argued that modern holistic education was based on two factors: humanist philosophies developed after World War II and the mid-1960s cultural paradigm shift. During the 1970s, the holism movement became mainstreamed, influencing the propagation of holistic education (Hayati, Fauzan, Iswari, & Khaidir, 2017). The emergence of holistic education inspired the creation of schools that used a holistic approach to learning. Waldorf schools founded by Rudolph Steiner were created as a response to the rapid change to social realities and to raise individuals capable of directing their own lives while benefiting society (Ensign, 1996). Steiner believed that both society and the individual are interdependent. Under this model, conscious personal transformation in a world characterized by a spiritual foundation, can lead to societal 9 transformations and spiritual enhancement (Ensign, 1996). He further believed that each child has deep unconscious forces that guide their behavior, and because of this Waldorf schools provide an environment where each child can experience classrooms on an intuitive level to help manifest their inner powers (Ensign, 1996).

Historical Roots of Holistic Education The holistic ideal can be traced back to indigenous cultures. In general, the aboriginal or indigenous person sees the earth and the universe as infused with meaning and Holistic educators try to recover this sense of meaning and purpose in education. (J, Miller 2004) The concept of holism comes from the Greek concept of holon that sees the universe as made up of integrated wholes that cannot be reduced in parts. (lee 1997) The Greeks argued for a holistic approach in learning. Socrates can be seen as a holistic educator because he encouraged each person to examine his or her own life: "know thyself." (J, Miller 2007). The holistic paradigm emerged as a vibrant and coherent intellectual movement in the 1980s and has been expressed by thinkers in divers fields. holistic education is not synonymous with the " New Age" movement, nor is it a product of the 1960s counterculture: it has deep roots in ancient spiritual traditions and cosmologies, which Aldous Huxley described as the perennial philosophy. When the so-called Enlightenment of the eighteenth century elevated analytical, scientific reason to near total dominance in the west, this perennial wisdom - the recognition of humanities intimate connection to the evolving cosmos – was relegated to a dissident movement labeled romanticism. Holistic education thus has its roots in the "romantic" educational theories of Jean Jacques Rousseau, Pestalozzy, and Frobel (R,Miller 1991a). Rousseau , Pestalozzy, and Frobel along with other holistic educaters of 19th and earle 20th centuries such as transcendentalists William Ellery, changing, rulf waldo emerson, Henry david Thoreau, Bronson Alcott, and fransis parker as well as Montessori and Rudolf Steiner, all emphasized the spiritual nature of the human being. (Brooks2006)

Objectives:

- 1) To find out the role of holistic education in optimum possible physical development of the students.
- 2) To find out the role of holistic education in optimum possible intellectual development of the students.
- 3) To find out the role of holistic education in optimum possible social development of students.

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

Methodology:

According to the objectives in the present study the descriptive survey method has been used. The aim of descriptive survey is to provide the description of some phenomenon set of factor. It is considered highly important because first hand data are gathered through it in a well organized manner on a particular subject. Such studies are conducted to collect detailed description of existing phenomenon that justification can be made on correct condition. In the present study under descriptive survey method college surveys were done to collect data. For this purpose 126 samples were selected from the three (comprising) higher educational institutions Tools Used in Data Collection: For collecting data investigator has used two tools. i) Questionnaire for Students ii) Interview for both Students and Teachers

History of Holistic Education

Holistic education is a relatively new movement developed in the 1980s to counteract the existing US learning structure that was perceived as mechanistic, according to Education Corner. However, the theory of educating based on a person's entire experience has roots in ancient concepts of instruction, including those of Greek and native indigenous cultures, and has increased in prevalence over the past century. Several different approaches based on whole-person education gained steam in the 20th century, including Maria Montessori's self-motivated growth philosophy and Rudolf Steiner and Emil Molt's Waldorf experiential learning technique.

Many states are now incorporating holistic goals into their educational system improvement plans. This trend is encouraged by the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA), which provides federal funding to foster state efforts. School systems are increasingly accepting the theory that learning conditions, whole-child services, and social and emotional development are measurable variables of education and can improve equity and outcomes, according to Education Counsel.

History of Holistic Learning

Holistic learning is a new movement that was developed in the 1980s to counteract the existing learning structure that was perceived as mechanistic. However, it is believed that the theory of educating based on a person's entire experience has roots in ancient concepts, including those of Greek and native indigenous cultures, and has gained importance over the past century. There have

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

been several different approaches based on whole-person education in the 20th century. Holistic Education is a method which focuses on preparing students to meet any challenges they may face in life and in their academic career. The most important theories behind holistic education are learning about oneself, developing health relationships and positive social behaviors, social and emotional development, resilience, and the ability to view beauty, experience transcendence and truth.

Methods of Holistic Learning:

The goal of holistic learning is to cultivate a developing child's physical, emotional, moral, psychological, and spiritual attributes. It provides opportunities that are personalized to a child's skills and feelings. Lessons are conducted in a safe, supportive environment that allows students to recognize their individual strengths. While holistic learning is guided by one philosophy, teachers can employ a number of methods and strategies to create a holistic learning culture.

Methods such as Experiential Learning where hands-on educational experiences are provided to students or Self-Guided learning where teachers allow students to learn at their own pace and whatever method the child is comfortable with allows students to grow not just academically but also is able to face challenges in the outside world

How teacher involvement helps in Holistic Learning?

Healthy Student-Teacher Relationships

When teachers are able to form strong bonds with students, their performance in class and engagement is positive. Students have a higher chance of success when they feel safe in a learning environment. Teachers should foster strong relationships by responding to students' strengths and needs and by acting in a culturally sensitive manner. Students should be allowed to help develop classroom rules and take on leadership roles. This encourages trust and communication among students and increases their motivation to do well.

Encouraging Self-Confidence

Students must feel they belong in school and have the potential to achieve. Teachers can help build self-confidence by providing different opportunities for students to learn and communicate what

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

they understand. Teachers should be able to recognize students' unique strengths and treat all students equally. Student motivation can be enhanced by making sure that lessons are relevant to students' lives and realistic.

Incorporating Emotional Reflection

Sometimes for a teacher, it's not always easy to look beyond academic performance to nurture the mental and emotional well-being of a child. To encourage emotional understanding in daily routines, teachers should provide certain time for students to reflect, contemplate, or meditate. Effective listening and observational skills might be the subject of lessons to promote empathy.

Holistic learning is based on a philosophy that brings a number of benefits to students, teachers, schools, and communities. Students are empowered to improve their academic prospects and gain the life skills necessary to succeed in their careers.

Here are 3 benefits of Holistic learning:

- **Improved Academic Achievement:** Holistic education can improve the academics of students regardless of background by catering to each student learning style and providing a supportive educational environment. The brain capacity of a student is increased when he/she feels physically and emotionally safe and has a good connection with the teacher.
- **Better Mental and Emotional Well-Being:** In a safe and supportive environment, where social and emotional learning is emphasized along with academics, students have a chance of imbibing qualities of self-awareness, confidence, and a sense of responsibility.
- **Developing Problem-Solving Abilities:** Students who are assigned with solving real-world problems that exist around them develop strong critical-thinking skills. These hands-on experiences give students the required skills that they will need in their careers, such as how to gather information, analyze, communicate effectively and how to collaborate and work with others.

Children not only require academic lessons, they need a system that helps them understand emotions, relationships and mental duress as well as develop resilience and team spirit. Holistic learning boosts the morale of a student so that they can go on to achieve success in their careers while becoming upstanding citizens of the society who contribute to the growth and development of

Received: 2 December 2023

Revised: 16 December 2023

Final Accepted 30 December 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451757>

the country. The holistic development of students is therefore crucial from the start of their academic years.

Conclusion:

Holistic education is an approach that can meet the needs of all types of learners and that mould future citizens who will contribute a concern and mindfulness for the society and the planet. Both global education and environmental education, which are also based on the principles of interdependence and connectedness, are embedded in it. Holistic education is an approach that can meet the needs of all types of learner, which prepares future citizens who will contribute towards a better world. Holistic education addressed the physical, intellectual, emotional, aesthetic and spiritual development of the students and put in place many of the values, attitudes and skills that will help the students to make a society of peace, where we can live in harmony with surrounding environment. The noble principles of holistic education must be reflected on teachers' way of thinking, their attitude and their teaching style. They should be seen as a friend, a mentor, a facilitator or an experienced travelling companion for the students. The students and the teachers should work together for the optimum possible development of students and these developments of students defiantly ensure a better world.

References:

- Hare John (2010): Holistic education: An interpretation for teachers in the IB programmes. • IB position paper: International Baccalaureate Organization.
- Kothari, C.R (1985): Research Methodology and Techniques. New Delhi, Wiley Eastern. • Koul Lokesh (1984): Methodology of Educational Research, Vikash Publishing House Pvt. Ltd.
- Taggart, G. (2001). Nurturing Spirituality: a rationale for holistic education. International Journal of Children's Spirituality, 6(3). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13644360120100496>
- UNESCO (1996). 'The four pillars of education', in Learning: The Treasure Within: Report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty First Century. Paris: UNESCO.
- Yoshida, A. (1996).
- "Holistic kyoiku ningengaku" ni mukete no shiron [An essay towards holistic pedagogical anthropology]. In Kyoikuteki nichijo no saikochiku [Reconstruction of educational reality], edited by S.Wada. Machida, Japan: TamagawaDaigaku Shuppanbu.